

Studies on the Dissociation Constants of 2,2'-Dipyridyl in Mixed Solvents

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In order to explore the role of the solvents on the 'iso-electric reactions' of the type $AH^+ \rightleftharpoons A + H^+$, the dissociation constants of 2, 2'-dipyridyl at low ionic strengths ($\approx 10^{-3}M$) were determined in different weight percentages of isopropanol-water mixtures (8, 16.3, 25.1, 34.3, 43.9, 54.0, 64.6, 75.8 and 87.5) and dioxane-water mixtures (10.3, 20.5, 30.6, 40.7, 50.8, 60.7, 70.6, 80.5, and 90.3) by pH-titration. The present results together with values obtained from previous experiments in ethanol-water and methanol-water mixtures were discussed in terms of ion-solvent interactions and solvent basicity.

IN order to explore the role of solvents on the dissociation constants of the "isoelectric" reactions of the type

the dissociation constants of 2,2'-dipyridyl (widely known for its analytical applications) were determined in different weight percentages of isopropanol-water and dioxane-water mixtures at low ionic strengths ($\approx 10^{-3}M$) by pH-titrations. The studies enable us to get information and insight regarding the different types of interactions in mixed solvents.

Experimental

Isopropanol (A.R., B.D.H.) was used by distilling it. Dioxane (A.R., B.D.H.) was refluxed for 48 hr with NaOH and distilled twice. It was then treated with metallic sodium, kept overnight and again distilled. The middle fractions of the solvents were utilised within 48 hr. The traces of water-content, if any, in the organic solvents were neglected.

Perchloric acid, caustic soda were of E. Merck's reagent grade and were estimated in the usual way. The solutions were made of double-distilled water.

The solutions of dipyridyl were prepared by directly weighing the reagent (G.R. E.M.) and dissolving in the appropriate solvents.

In our measurement of the dissociation constants of 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-dipyridyl in mixed solvents by spectrophotometric method, it has been found that the accuracy of determination of pK —ultimately depends on the accuracy of the measurement of H^+ ions in mixed solvents¹. We, therefore, preferred to determine the dissociation constants of dipyridyl in iso-propanol-water and dioxane-water mixtures by pH-titration. Definite amounts of the ligand were taken in a number of volumetric flasks, acidified to different extents (30% to 70%) with known quantities of perchloric acid and the meter

readings were taken. The experiments were repeated with different concentrations (5×10^{-3} – $1 \times 10^{-2}M$) of the ligand and in different percentages of the mixed solvents.

The weight percentages of the organic solvents in mixed solvents were calculated from the known amounts of the two solvents by volumes and their density values² at 25°. The reliability of this method of preparing a solvent mixture of given weight-composition was checked by determining the densities of mixed solvents and comparing with reported density values. A slight disagreement was noted. The dielectric constants of different iso-propanol-water and dioxane-water mixtures were calculated from the data of Akerlof and Short.³

The pH-meter readings were taken with a Cambridge Bench type battery operated pH-meter. The measurements were taken at 25°.

Results

The thermodynamic dissociation constants K_T for the equilibrium

(A = 2,2'-dipyridyl) is represented as

$$K_T = \frac{a_A \times a_{H^+}}{a_{AH^+}} = \frac{C_A \times C_{H^+}}{C_{AH^+}} \times \frac{f_A \times f_{H^+}}{f_{AH^+}} \quad \dots (2)$$

Since the ionic strengths of the solutions were low (in the range 1.5 – $7.0 \times 10^{-3}M$), $\frac{f_A \times f_{H^+}}{f_{AH^+}}$ can be approximated to unity. Even in concentrated solutions, $f_{H^+} = f_{AH^+}$ (due to same charge types and f_A equal to unity). Slight deviation may arise due to different ion-size parameter of H^+ and AH^+ ions.

Thus,

$$pK_T = pH + \log \frac{C_{AH^+}}{C_A}$$

$$= B + \log U_H + \log \frac{C_{AH^+}}{C_A} \quad \dots (3)$$

B = meter-readings in mixed-solvents.

$\log U_H$ = correction factor in mixed solvents.

$\log \frac{C_{AH^+}}{C_A}$ was determined from the fraction of neutralisation. The glass electrode in different mixed solvents were calibrated in the same way as previously described⁴⁻⁶ before each set of measurements and $\log U_H$ values were determined.

The pK values in different mixed solvents together with our values in methanol-water and ethanol-water mixtures are given in Table 1.

The pK values at zero percent of organic solvents from different types of extrapolations come out to be

	(i)	(ii)	(iii)
Methanol-water mixtures	4.54	4.48	4.47
Ethanol-water mixtures	4.33	4.32	4.26
Isopropanol-water mixtures	4.47	4.40	4.39
Dioxane-water mixtures	4.42	4.46	4.38

From the results, it is apparent that whatever might be the extrapolations, for any particular solvent systems, the pK -values in water comes out to be the same within experimental errors. For different solvent systems, however, the error is appreciable. This might be due to different solvation properties of ions in different mixed solvents. However, the pK -values for water obtained from different extrapolations are within reasonable agreement with our value 4.47 ± 0.02 at 25° obtained spectrophotometrically. The small deviations are likely to occur

TABLE 1. DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF 2, 2'-DIPYRIDYL AT VARIOUS ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Wt. % of methanol	pK	Wt. % of ethanol	pK	Wt. % of isopropanol	pK	Wt. % of dioxane	pK
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
8.0	4.40	8.0	4.20	8.0	4.23	10.3	4.25
16.4	4.25	16.4	4.04	16.3	4.00	20.5	4.08
25.2	4.15	25.3	3.91	25.2	3.71	30.6	3.87
34.4	4.01	34.4	3.72	34.3	3.45	40.7	3.71
44.1	3.83	44.0	3.48	43.9	3.23	50.8	3.56
54.2	3.60	54.1	3.20	54.0	3.06	60.7	3.41
64.7	3.32	64.7	3.10	64.6	2.96	70.6	3.24
75.9	3.15	76.0	2.89	75.8	2.88	80.5	3.21
87.6	3.04	87.6	2.79	87.5	2.82	90.3	3.23

Discussions

The pK -value of 2,2'-dipyridyl in water reported in the literature varies from 4.25 to 4.51.⁷ In order to verify the results, we determined the pK value spectrophotometrically at low ionic-strengths ($\approx 10^{-4}M$). The value obtained in 4.47 ± 0.02^1 in very good agreement with the values 4.48 or 4.51 ± 0.02 reported by Irving and co-workers.⁸

The pK values show linear-relationship when plotted against (i) weight percentage of organic solvents, (ii) mole-fractions of organic solvents, and (iii) $1/D$ in different mixed solvents (nearly upto 60% by wt. of organic solvents.).

Deviations at higher percentages of organic solvents may be due to inaccuracy of H^+ ion concentration measurement from pH -meter readings arising from (a) high liquid-junction potential of uncertain magnitude, (b) low sensitivity of the glass electrode, (c) solute-solvent interactions.

from different extrapolations. However, the deviations in results are found to be greatest in ethanol-water mixtures.

All these reactions are 'iso-electric' in character. Therefore, the change in dielectric constant should have little effect except in little changes in free energy resulting from the small differences of the radii of ions. However, large changes in free-energy suggest that solute-solvent interactions rather than electro-static effect have greater influence on pK -values. This is also borne out by similar observations by Marshall⁹ and Bates¹⁰. The decrease in pK values can be attributed to the increase in the solubility of the neutral ligand in organic solvents leading to greater dissociation of AH^+ molecules. The solubility of the ligand together with the solvational properties of H^+ and dipy H^+ would determine the change in pK values.¹

We are unable to see any minimum in pK values for the reaction $AH^+ \rightleftharpoons A + H^+$ though a minimum

in the pK -values is generally observed¹⁰ around 70 wt. % of methanol, 80 wt. % of ethanol and 86 wt. % of isopropanol. We have reservations regarding our values at the two highest percentages of organic solvents.

The correction factor values, however, were found to be highest around 65–70 wt. % of organic solvents except in case of dioxane.

The plots of pK against $1/D$ give straight lines with slopes and intercepts different. The results indicate that the solute-solvent interactions are of great importance in the study of the dissociation constants. Comparison of the pK -values from the equielectric mixtures of different solvent compositions may give some idea regarding the non-electrostatic parts of different solvent compositions. In view of uncertainties of radii values of different ions (specially in case of unsymmetrical electrolytes) and the lack of exact knowledge of solvation, the basicity of the solvent mixtures could not be ascertained but only the relative idea regarding the non-electrostatic contributions could be made.¹¹

In order to throw more light, it is necessary to divide ΔpK into $\Delta pK(\text{el})$ and $\Delta pK(\text{nonel})$ as $\Delta pK = \Delta pK(\text{el}) + \Delta pK(\text{nonel})$.

The knowledge of $\Delta pK(\text{el})$ is thus essential to calculate $\Delta pK(\text{nonel})$. $\Delta pK(\text{el})$ can be calculated using modified Born^{12,13} equations, if we know the accurate values of the radii of the different ions. The free energy of transfer of free-base is also necessary. In view of our inadequate knowledge of the accurate values of radii of ions and due to the limitations of the method of evaluating ΔpK_{el} , ΔpK_{nonel} of the mixed solvents were not calculated. But for the "isoelectric" reactions of the type $\text{AH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{A} + \text{H}^+$, ΔpK_{el} can be assumed to be almost constant as a first approximation throughout the solvent composition. Thus, the changes in ΔpK represents primarily the change of ΔpK_{nonel} , which is governed to a large extent by solute-solvent interactions and

the results indicate that the solute-solvent interactions are maximum in the region 60–80 wt. % of organic solvents.^{1,11}

The present state of our knowledge is yet inadequate to provide satisfactory answer of the various problems associated with solution chemistry particularly the role of the solvents on the dissociation constants of the ligands. Systematic studies are necessary to make up the deficiencies.

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